

MARKETING AND INFORMATION PROVISION IN ENHANCING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT

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Abstract : The scientific article analyze important aspects dry as methods of marketing research in public transport enterprises , the role of information oath their impact on the enterprise oath the population , the prevention of traffic congestion oath environmental degradation on urban roads .

Key words : public transport , marketing , demarketing , branding , information , internet , software .

Citizens have a choice between public transport and private transport, but it should be distinguished by the high quality, convenience and reliability of the public transport service. At the same time, despite the fact that the quality of service is of primary importance for a future customer, its image and the availability of information about it are also important.

There are a number of difficulties in the application of marketing research in public transport due to the specific characteristics of the marketing service in public transport. Transportation systems resources limited because of , customers the number to multiply directed strategies , public transport marketing i _ sharp which cannot be popularized to the situation take coming can _ Such in the circumstances is available customers save to stay and to them more good service to show provide in order to less aggressive short term strategy with start to the goal is appropriate . Summary by doing in other words , transport system passengers number significant to growth ready to be need _ However , it is important social to the role have and less in quantity to the budget have public transport companies sometimes new products or service types change opportunity have they won't be .

We can see statistical data on the number of passengers transported and passenger traffic in the Republic by types of transport in Table 1.

Table 1

Passenger transportation and passenger circulation by public transport types in the Republic of Uzbekistan¹

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Transported passengers , million people	539.4	564.4	255.9	380.9	431.2
<i>including:</i>					
railway	22.1	22.9	6.2	7.9	9.0
airway	2.6	3.2	0.9	3.0	4.1
car ^{*)}	440.7	454.5	208.5	265.4	277.9
city electricity	74.0	83.8	40.4	104.6	140.2
<i>including:</i>					
tram	4.4	3.8	1.2	2.3	2.9
trolleybus	0.5	0.7	0.3	0.5	0.5
metropolitan	69.1	79.2	38.8	101.8	136.7
Passenger turnover, mln. passenger-km	17,967.5	20,566.0	7 543.9	12 307.6	19 177.3
<i>including:</i>					
railway	4 329.0	4 385.2	1 794.9	3 130.2	3 549.4
airway	8 842.3	10,998.1	3 013.8	5 258.8	10,905.4
car ^{*)}	4 251.3	4 564.7	2 438.9	3 154.5	3 701.3
city electric	544.9	618.0	296.3	764.1	1 021.2
<i>including:</i>					
tram	26.2	20.5	4.2	7.9	9.7
trolleybus	15.0	19.9	9.1	14.3	14.8
metropolitan	503.7	577.6	283.0	741.9	996.7

If we pay attention to the statistical data, we can see that the rate of passenger transport by general transport types is growing by an average of 2.8% annually and by an average of 11.9% between 2018 and 2022 (Figure 1).

During the years 2018-2022, the largest part of the number of passengers transported by all types of transport, i.e. 98 percent, corresponds to the share of road transport.

¹ www.stat.uz

1 . Transported passengers, million people

The composition of future customers in public transport is very diverse, they include the elderly, students, teenagers, all of whom have different lifestyles, habits, needs and reasons for traveling (business trip, leisure or shopping trip). In addition, they use different data channels, so they need to be addressed in different ways. Thus, sometimes targeted marketing campaigns containing different advertising sections for different customer groups may be more effective, given that different customer groups do not react the same to service changes. For example, price changes had an impact on the number of people choosing public transport for business trips: a 17% increase in the price of a road ticket in the city of Tashkent limited people's ability to use public transport in some cases, the increase in prices did not affect the improvement of services, passengers using public transport as a means of getting to work the number has partially decreased, so convenience and price level are important for this group.

There is no doubt that improving service with a marketing strategy is more likely to attract new customers. For example , in Perth , Scotland , a transport company has a low floor buses current reach marketing campaign with _ started _ With that together , local power by more bus stops installed and in the city public transport priority guaranteed . In general community _ _ transport mode transition society for is useful because in general on the roads movement level decreases.

Perth's marketing strategy involved advertising, telephone conversations with prospective customers, and free offers. As a result, two years after the

campaign, there was a 56% increase in the number of passengers, the tendency of the population to switch from private transport to public transport.

A similar situation was found in the city of Buckingham, Great Britain, where the public transport company could not improve the service and attract the desired customers, and decided to develop a marketing strategy, which resulted in a 42% increase in the number of bus trips per year.

According to Embarq-Brasil, information provision in public transport is the various elements used in the transport system to facilitate navigation for passengers, regardless of their capabilities, age and literacy levels.

Various reasons according to one row transport companies in cases service show about information to give they don't want Some companies local population anyway own products about they know that to believe maybe others _ in detail information need not that to think because it is possible customer always from the driver or need if of the company from the representative to ask can _ Information get possible have of not being again one reason is that the enterprise work of ability low , this to the image take will come and service about information present If not , it's the customer's attitude break can _ Mostly transport companies their own services about information buses inside or at bus stops vocal messages with provide , however this measures car drivers public to transport attraction in doing efficient not because they are normal they don't use and this on the ground present done from the data limited they stay .

Although the information is becoming more widespread, it is not clear whether it can change the overall travel pattern of passengers, as they probably tend to use the same mode of transport without considering alternatives.

When traveling by car, people feel in control of the journey, but not in public transport: in such a situation, a person often has to change or use different transport companies with different sources of information. Since there are many transport companies and each of them has its own communication platform, people get confused about it. In most cases, people are aware of the local service, but they

don't know what is offered outside of their area. In addition, there are people who decide to change their place of residence, and they form a specific group, because if they are not informed about the transport service in the new place, they can continue to use the car they are in. used to. Thus, transport companies should develop cooperation with local authorities, real estate agencies and movers, inform them about their services in order to reach potential customers. In an unfamiliar environment, people should be given an overview of the transport service in the area by all the transport companies to show them the whole system and give them a choice.

Marketing of public transport provides an opportunity for transport companies to promote their products, but in addition, it has a certain positive effect on consumers, as it creates the image of the company . When this company is seen as a modern, quality service provider, the passengers who use it and partially join it are more satisfied. Service-related features affect consumers. If the service is perceived as unsafe and only available to low-income populations, people will be more likely to switch to car ownership once they have access to it, especially if car ownership is perceived as a sign of prosperity. Promotional mechanisms for private transport also work in public transport advertising, so if the image of the service is good, people may like to join it. However, in many cases, public transport has a bad reputation compared to the car, which seems very attractive to consumers, especially when transport companies do not put enough effort into developing their marketing strategies. In fact, there are many positive aspects of public transport: they are stable, sometimes faster than cars due to traffic jams, and can appear as an independent choice of a smart person who values time and prefers a car, not because it is the only option available. Public transport is often perceived as a means of transport for those who do not own a car, and it is important to change this perception and present public transport as a viable alternative to private vehicles. However, this is a difficult task, as the car is still a very comfortable means of transport and public transport needs to provide quality service to reduce

the comfort level gap. At the same time, it is clear from the examples analyzed above that improving the service without adequate advertising and marketing may not be enough to attract passengers.

In addition, since the development of strategies for attracting people, establishing separate lanes for public transport, further expanding the market, and developing strategies for moving at fixed times, it can also be a means of service development, because it allows the company to learn more about the needs and requirements of customers. allows.

Marketing strategies with shared transportation companies information supply system work output need _ Sometimes people from the car to use preferred they see because they are some one in the area public transport service about they don't know

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